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Conflict-Resolution *Skripts*: A Problem Analysis Paper

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Abstract

This paper is submitted in fulfillment of a doctoral-level Leadership course requirement to analyze and solve a community problem by synthesizing Frankena's (1966) five-boxes model and methodology from Ries's (2011) lean start-up model. This analysis considers questions of culture and context, and introduces the concept of *skripts*, a model founded on research with client couples working to resolve relational conflict.

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"Mawage. Mawage is wot bwings us togeder today. Mawage, that bwessed awangment, that dweam wifin a dweam..."
 – Peter Cook as *The Impressive Clergyman*, *The Princess Bride* (1987)

Conflictual marriage: A problem for analysis

Marriage is a solemn affair. It orders adult life and has the power to bring joy to all who are touched by it. But too often, it is undertaken by individuals who lack the tools to tap into the best aspects of that important institution. This paper addresses solutions to the problem of poor – and contentious – marital communication, using the problem-solving models of William K. Frankena (1966) and Eric Ries (2011).

The Frankena Model

Frankena's normative philosophy model proposes a five-step practical syllogism (Bagheri Noaparast, K., & Noaparast, 2015), a line of reasoning to be used in analyzing and solving problems, namely:

- A. **Normative disposition.** A value proposition—a statement of basic values, principles, ends, abilities, skills, character traits, beliefs, or body of knowledge—that are elemental to living "a good or a moral life" (Frankena, 1966, p. 10). "*Goal X is valuable.*"

- B. **Factual premise.** Empirical, theological, or philosophical evidence that the normative disposition is worthwhile. "*Here's why Goal X is valuable.*"
- C. **Call to action.** The normative conclusion. "*Therefore we must achieve Goal X.*"
- D. **Ways and means.** Recommendations for achieving Goal X founded on observation and experience. "*Method Y is necessary, effective, or helpful*" (1966, p. 11).
- E. **Conclusion.** Second call to action. "*Therefore Method Y should be used.*" (1966, p. 11).

The ABC portion of the model Frankena (1966) identifies as the *philosophical* argument; the CDE pattern he calls the *practical* argument (p. 12). Between the philosophical and the practical, Frankena proposes a rational process from identifying a goal to ensuring its achievement. (Figure 1, introduced later in this paper, diagrams the Frankena process.)

The Ries Model

The Ries (2011) Lean Startup model presupposes the problem *and* the solution, and ventures from there directly to implementation. The goal of the Ries model "is to figure out [what] customers want...as quickly as possible, [emphasizing] fast iteration and customer insight, a huge vision, and great ambition, all at the same time" (loc 284).

Ries' philosophy is that entrepreneurship, and its stepsister leadership, are everywhere to be found, that the enterprising leader will assuredly fail, and that winning the game entails being the fastest to fail, as failure creates learning, and learning eventually leads to success.

The lean startup process, illustrated in Figure 2, entails the following three-step iterative cycle:

- A. **Build.** Most entrepreneurs, Ries asserts, spend too much time and money building, which magnifies failure. The key to speeding up the failure-then-success cycle is to build the minimum viable product (MVP) – a buggy, terrible, unstable product that nevertheless secures initial customers (Ries, 2011, loc 135).
- B. **Measure.** Launching the MVP – a landing page, perhaps, or a mockup, an individualized product, or a manual process – provides immediate data about whether the product is viable, finds a market, is correctly priced, or solves an actual problem. Measuring generally involves A-B testing, or other test processes that generate data about buyer behavior.
- C. **Learn.** In the best possible world, the MVP is a roaring success and buyers fight to purchase the product. In this exceptional case, the entrepreneur learns that the product may be underpriced, and can pivot (a lean startup behavior) the pricing to a new level. In all other cases, the data enable the entrepreneur to eliminate less successful behaviors as determined by testing, and iterate the product or the marketing to new levels of success.

Applying the Models

Because the Frankena model boils down to a simple syllogism, it is possible to develop a brief statement invoking all five elements—or boxes—of the model. In the context of marriage: “Marriage is a social good and should be protected. Unfortunately, certain conflictual spousal behaviors have been shown empirically to lead to the breakdown of marriages.

Therefore, to protect marriage, it is necessary to substitute for negative conflictual behaviors positive ones. One practical way to facilitate beneficial behaviors is to introduce conflict management *scripts*. Because these scripts work to reduce conflict, this is a recommended method.”

Each of these statements must be expanded, and evidence introduced, if one is to make a persuasive argument. The evidence-based reasoning looks like this:

- A. Equitable marriage is a social good, and should be protected (c.f., Waite & Gallagher, 2000; Wells & Zinn, 2004; National Pastoral Initiative for Marriage, n.d.). Marriage is a beneficial social institution for the nurturance of children as well as an institution that facilitates the maturation and overall well being of individuals (Nock, 2005; Powell, 2009; Riber, 2004).
- B. Relational conflict behaviors predict divorce (Birditt et al., 2010 citing numerous other studies). The Birditt team argues that “destructive behaviors result in negative evaluations of marriage and declines in marital satisfaction and stability, whereas constructive behaviors lead to improvements in evaluations of marriage and increases in marital satisfaction and stability.”
- C. To protect marriage, it is necessary to decrease conflict behaviors and increase protective behaviors. In support of this call to action, Fowers (1998) argues that skills training in conflict resolution is seen by many therapists as the most important part of marital therapy (p. 522).
- D. There are a number of strategies that couples employ to decrease conflict, though strategies found in the academic research tend to be more theoretical, and less practical. Such categorizations as “communication styles, ambivalence-based versus satiation-based conditional use, and proactivity/passivity” (Baxter & Dindia, 1990), as well as self-disclosure, editing, and non-defensive listening (Fowers, 1998) typify these imprecise

strategies.

This paper argues instead for training conflict-saturated couples in the use of very specific scripts. The author, a marriage and family therapist, has observed that knowing exactly what to say, and when to say it, facilitates social functioning and provides the foundation for relational connection. To this end, the author has developed a collection of scripts (for which the German spelling *skripts*¹ is preferred, to distinguish them from the more commonly used English spelling that is generally understood in psychological contexts to refer to cultural life-scripts [c.f., Tungjitharoen & Berntsen, 2020] or internalized world views [Sabghir, 1982]). Hundreds of client couples have adopted these *skripts* in their own marriages, and have provided enthusiastically positive feedback, as well as occasional suggestions for small amendments. These *skripts* have the effect of decreasing conflict behaviors and increasing protective ones.

- E. Because these *skripts* have been shown to reduce marital conflict, they should be included in couple's relational communication tool set.

Frankena's syllogism is useful for conceptualizing a problem and its solution, but for all its good intent, its passive-voiced "should be used" does not provide an implementable procedure for promulgating an idea.

Hence, Ries. The beauty of Ries' entrepreneurial model is that it advocates for immediate implementation of a proposed solution at the lowest possible financial investment, albeit at a high risk of failure. As a business owner, the author of this paper is already well acquainted with, and has used with some success, Ries' model. Many years ago, the state department of health issued my first counseling qualification based on my undergraduate and law-school studies, and so I was able to open a private therapy practice while still in graduate school. That was the first Ries-ian *build*. I A-B tested initial marketing

materials, and was gratified to discover one promotional approach that brought a large number of couple clients to my door almost immediately. That was my first *measure*. Over the intervening years, I have listened to and learned from hundreds of couples while continuing my academic and independent studies. This has been my preliminary *learn*.

Eventually, my learning was distilled into a number of specific tools – *skripts* – that I shared with clients to facilitate their attempts to communicate with one another more effectively. The second *build*. As clients implemented the tools, I sought feedback on what did and didn't work. The second *measure*. From that feedback I was able to *learn* what resonated and what fell flat.

Now comes the third iteration of the Ries cycle. The *skripts* have been exceptionally successful at decreasing or even eliminating the contention between husbands and wives—so successful, in fact, that it seems inhumane not to share them with greater numbers of people. Sharing them widely requires scaling. There are not enough hours in the day to coach the *skripts* to millions, or even thousands, of couples on a one-to-one basis. In order to scale, it is necessary to publish.

Unfortunately, the *Build-Measure-Learn* process at this third level leaves far less room for failure than could be absorbed in the early iterations. If I fail with a single client, that person can fire me and find a more compatible therapist. Failure at the publishing stage is dispositive for further opportunities. So the *build* portion of this iteration requires a bigger investment of time and testing. The MVP of that build portion involves three elements:

- A. building credibility, facilitated by undertaking doctoral-level academic studies. It also involves
- B. conducting replicable research to verify clinical observations, which comes as part of the PhD dissertation process and submission to academic journals. Finally, it requires
- C. publishing those findings in academic journals and commercial media.

¹ Whether to pluralize using the Germanic *e* suffix or the *s* is an open question, though given the English-

language context in which this idea is being proposed, *s* seems more comprehensible if less grammatical.

Ries' *measure* portion can be more straightforward. Not all measurements can be conducted via A-B testing, but beta testing early drafts of articles and books directed at a lay readership is one measurement mechanism.

While working through the *build* portion, it is possible to simultaneously *measure* and test the market by growing an email list, publishing in periodicals and online media, creating online courses, and increasing a social media presence. What is *learned* from that testing will aid in determine which publishing path – commercial or self-publishing – to pursue.

Conclusion

This analysis contemplates the significance of marriage in building happiness, and seeks ways to help the largest number of couples strengthen their intimate relationships. It considers practical mechanisms for widely introducing a particular model of relationship conflict resolution. This paper also demonstrates that in the context of the Frankena and Ries problem-solving models it may be possible to produce an organizational plan for publishing tested theories.

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